

METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL AND PERSONAL QUALITIES OF PRINCIPALS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *The article examines the peculiarities of researching the professional and personal qualities of the principals of preschool educational institutions.*

Key words: *professional qualities, management activity, responsibility, independence, striving for the goal, determination.*

The process of developing the professional and personal potential of the director of the preschool educational institution envisages monitoring in this direction.

As a result of the analysis of psychological and psychological literature, it was found that the personal and professional preparation of a person for the activity of the director of a preschool educational institution consists of three components:

1) motivational-value component, related to understanding the purpose of activity, emotional positive attitude to one's profession;

2) the cognitive-volitional component represents the characteristics of the development of professionally important personal qualities of MTM directors;

3) the operational-practical component represents a set of professional knowledge and skills that allow the director of a preschool educational institution to perform management functions.

Based on psychological and psychological research, the following indicators representing the motivational and valuable component of the personal capabilities of the principals of the preschool educational institution were distinguished:

satisfaction with professional activity;

self-assessment of the development of abilities for psychological activity;

development of motivation for professional activity.

Satisfaction with professional psychological activity includes the following indicators:

- the level of development of interest in one's work,
- satisfaction with the achievements of one's psychological activity,
- creative satisfaction from one's work,
- level of development of professional responsibility,
- material satisfaction consisting of the level of prioritizing a high salary over the work process,
- satisfaction with interactions with the directorate,
- satisfaction with relationships with colleagues,
- communicative satisfaction,
- level of aspiration to professional activity.

These indicators are a general indicator of the director of a preschool educational institution's satisfaction with his work.

Also, M.V. Mostepanenko tried to give a popular expression of the above understanding of method and methodology: "The way of knowing, based on a specific set of previously acquired general knowledge, is a method. Methodology is the teaching of the principles and methods of knowledge. Due to the fact that the method is related to preliminary knowledge, the methodology is divided into two parts:

a) teaching about the principles and primary foundations of knowledge;

b) teaching about methods and techniques based on those principles. Evaluation and analysis of perceptions and views by the researcher in the process of cognition is the first part of cognition. This part of the methodology is directly related to philosophy, worldview. The general aspects of the specific methods of knowledge that make up its general methodology are interpreted in the teaching on research methods. This definition excludes the limitation of understanding as a set of technical means, methods of organizing research, or the basis of knowledge, both philosophical and worldview.

The second type of scientific view is characteristic of positivist scientists and denies the role of worldview in knowledge. Understanding the term methodology in a narrow sense, seeing it as a synonym of methodology is also found in the works of former Soviet researchers. V.A. Yadov does not include any of the three stages that he distinguished from the methodological analysis. As a result, the methodological status of the organization of the research, the implementation aspect, and the methodological side are deprived of reflection. For the same reason, it is desirable to understand the essence and importance of methodological analysis, to distinguish the characteristics of researchers' use of terms. Many researchers understand the concept of "method" more narrowly, as a result, they are not limited to defining methodology as a teaching about the method of scientific knowledge. According to E.G. Yudin's definition of methodology, it is a teaching about means, methods, logical organization and structure of activity.

Although the term "methodology" in our study is close to the above interpretations, it has some differences both in form and content. The study subject of the methodology of psychology includes information on the subject, criteria, categories, principles, laws, mechanisms, properties, qualities, stages, phases of development, approaches of the science. In our opinion, when thinking about the methodology, there can certainly be a special form of reflection, sharing information about self-awareness. In psychology, self-awareness is a particular form of information system that has a complex nature of scientific knowledge. At this point, it is important to reflect on the ways to determine the internal and external determinants of cognitive processes, to provide information on its structure, critical evaluation of acquired knowledge, and description of its connection with practice.

In psychology, many theoretical psychologists emphasize that the emotional life of a person is the factor that ensures the success of behavior, behavior and activity. We have no objection to the veracity of this interpretation. Due to the fact that experimental psychology is separate as a field, this factor is included in the subject of research. The successful completion of a person's activity, behavior and behavior largely depends on a person's emotional states, experiences and high feelings. If the successful course of activities, the manifestation of behavior in interpersonal relations is evaluated as a positive psychological state, it is recognized that emotions and feelings prevail in a stable direction towards the goal. The presence of qualities of

strength, stability, and perfection of feelings means that they have become dynamic stereotypes. A person's relationship with nature and society - causes a periodic and temporary change in the norms of dealing with them.

The implementation of human activity and behavior based on certain laws depends on both objective and subjective conditions. It consists of objective conditions, that is, micro and macro, that is, material existence, the availability of auxiliary means, the ability to meet their requirements, the interference of external stimuli, the compatibility of time and space dimensions. The presence of a system of natural conditions for the manifestation of behavior and activity serves as factors that ensure their success. In addition to failure in natural conditions, the occurrence of certain deficiencies and interruptions causes defects.

Due to changes in objective and subjective conditions, the priority of positive or negative psychological states, events, traits, and experiences occurs. This reduces the activity of the higher nervous system, the rhythm of the central nervous system (CNS), and the ability to work. As a result of this, the usual efforts, operations, rituals in the implementation of activity, behavior, behavior begin to be disturbed. Extreme nervousness, mental defect, deviance from law, rule of unpleasant experiences lead. The success of activity, behavior and behavior will be questioned. The dominance of self-productivity, stability, and goal-orientation qualities will disappear. As a result, unfulfilled good intentions and high emotions continue to reign as dreams.

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